

(Table 1 contd.)

Formamide (FA)	200 (9 763) 246 (19 256) 259 (26 680)	200 (11 061) 246 (18 563) 261 (27 757)	200 (9 728) 246 (18 120) 260 (26 653)	200 (9 690) 246 (16 602) 272 (26 912)	201 (11 911) 245 (19 916) 273 (26 731)	204 (9 961) 245 (18 320) 274 (29 522)	206 (11 711) 244 (17 321) 276 (27 420)	204 (12 220) 243 (18 416) 275 (26 594)	205 (12 261) 242 (18 520) 274 (26 910)	208 (12 219) 250 (16 421) 278 (26 541)	209 (10 281) 250 (15 821) 277 (26 520)	210 (9 771) 251 (18 830) 269 (24 503)
-------------------	--	---	--	--	---	--	---	---	---	---	---	--

TABLE 2—SOLVENT SENSITIVITY OF CARBOXYALKYL THIOCARBAMIDES (1-12)

Compd. no.	Thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions			Carboxyaryl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions			Carboxyaryl $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions		
	ΔE_T^\ddagger	$E_T = ms + b$		ΔE_T^\ddagger	$E_T = ms + b$		ΔE_T^\ddagger	$E_T = ms + b$	
	kcal mol ⁻¹	m	ms** kcal mol ⁻¹	kcal mol ⁻¹	m	ms** kcal mol ⁻¹	kcal mol ⁻¹	m	ms** kcal mol ⁻¹
1	1.91	0.066	2.05	3.88	0.122	3.79	2.77	0.102	3.17
2	2.40	0.081	2.51	4.40	0.138	4.29	3.42	0.113	3.51
3	2.93	0.099	2.76	4.05	0.129	4.01	6.40	0.223	6.93
4	3.91	0.124	3.85	3.18	0.098	3.04	4.88	0.151	4.69
5	3.92	0.130	4.04	2.77	0.096	2.98	4.20	0.147	4.57
6	2.85	0.091	2.83	2.80	0.092	2.86	4.13	0.138	4.29
7	3.38	0.120	3.73	3.57	0.118	3.66	4.12	0.126	3.91
8	2.89	0.094	2.92	3.49	0.104	3.23	4.17	0.129	4.01
9	2.89	0.097	3.01	3.21	0.108	3.35	3.21	0.105	3.26
10	3.27	0.110	3.42	3.46	0.114	3.54	4.74	0.149	4.63
11	2.84	0.093	2.89	3.49	0.113	3.51	3.98	0.107	3.32
12	2.80	0.093	3.04	3.46	0.115	3.57	4.04	0.136	4.23

* Defined as the difference between ethylene glycol and benzene transition energies. ** Values should be compared with those in column ΔE_T .

carbamides and the electrons from the propyl group are donated to carboxyl group where these are delocalised with the thiocarbonyl group, there by increasing the electron density for the ground level. So lesser energy is required for the excitation and hence position of λ_{max} is shifted to longer wavelength for $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ carboxyalkyl transitions and to shorter wavelength for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ thiocarboxyl transitions.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. K. Arora, Head, Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, H.A.U., Hisar for providing UV-VIS spectrophotometer and one of the authors (P.S.M.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial help.

References

1. B. DASH and S. K. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 738; O. P. KHURANA, J. S. TYAGI and A. D. TANEJA, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 29, 185; J. D. GAUBA, A. D. TANEJA and J. S. TYAGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 138.
2. P. S. MITTAL, N. KUMAR and A. D. TANEJA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 382.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1962.
4. C. N. R. RAO, "Ultraviolet and Visible Spectroscopy", Butterworths, London, 1967.

5. E. S. STERN and O. J. TIMMONS, "Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", Edward Arnold, London, 1970.
6. E. M. KOSOWER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 3267.

A Novel Route for Progenitors of Carbazoles with a View to Study Larvicidal Properties

(Miss) B. CHOUDHURY

Durgapur Women's College, Durgapur
and

B. ROY CHOUDHURY and B. P. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235
Manuscript received 15 February 1988, revised 10 May 1988,
accepted 23 August 1988

CARBAZOLE compounds possess various biological activities¹⁻³. Due to co-occurrence of carbazole alkaloids glycozoline and glycozolidine with furoquinoline and acridine bases in *Glycosmis pentaphylla*, Chakraborty *et al.*¹ considered that carbazole alkaloids from higher plants are of anthranilate origin. They further considered that diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid and diphenylamine are also possible biogenetic precursors of carbazole alkaloids¹. Diphenyl amine or *N*-methyldiphenylamine also undergoes photolytic cyclisation to carbazole or *N*-methylcarbazole⁴. Carruthers⁵ synthesised the carbazole alkaloid glycozoline by

photocyclisation of the appropriate diphenyl amine. Carbazole can be obtained by thermal cyclisation, of diphenyl amine at red-heat, but Chakraborty *et al.*¹ showed that in presence of elemental iodine and oxygen the cyclisation can be carried out in good yield at 350° in a sealed tube⁶. The thermal decarboxylation of diphenylamine to carbazole can be carried out at lower temperature using degassed Raney nickel at 250°. In a sealed tube the reaction takes place in presence of *p*-cymene at 182°⁷. The carbazole alkaloids, glycozoline and glycozolidine have also been synthesised from diphenylamines⁸. Diphenylamine also possesses pesticidal activity⁹. All these interested us to study the larvicidal activities of anthranilic acid and diphenylamine derivatives, which are the progenitors of carbazoles. During this study we prepared diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid by a novel method and confirmed its structure by spectral measurements. Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid on decarboxylation gave diphenylamine (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Anthranilic acid was refluxed with solid sodium nitrite in chloroform medium for 5 h. The chloroform solution on extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution gave water-soluble product, which on acidification with HCl at pH 5.5–6 furnished a reddish precipitate, which on repeated crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene mixture gave a nitrogeous crystalline compound, m.p. 184°; found to be homogeneous by tlc. It was soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution with evolution of CO₂ (presence of COOH group); soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetone and alcohol but sparingly soluble in petroleum ether; gave deep violet colour with concentrated H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ mixture or concentrated H₂SO₄ and NaNO₂, but no colour with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution; the compound was analysed for C₁₁H₁₁NO₂ (M⁺ 213). The uv absorption maxima of the compound (vide Experimental) indicated the presence of a diphenylamine nucleus. The ir (KBr) spectra showed peaks at 3 360 (NH), 1 645 (COOH) and 1 570 cm⁻¹ (aromatic residue). The ¹H nmr (90 MHz, CDCl₃)

showed signals of nine protons (eight at δ 7.0–7.45 and one at δ 6.8), one proton at δ 8.1 (NH) and one proton at δ 9.4 (COOH); hence ¹H nmr spectra account for all the 11 protons in the compound.

Considering m.p., properties and spectral data, and comparing with the literature value, the acid was identified as diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid.

Mechanism of the formation: Anthranilic acid on diazotisation by sodium nitrite in aqueous medium and keeping at room temperature should give salicylic acid. But on diazotisation by sodium nitrite at reflux temperature it gives diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid via benzyne intermediate. Sodium nitrite reacts with anthranilic acid and forms benzyne via zwitterion. Benzyne reacts with another mole of anthranilic acid and eliminates a proton and forms diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (Scheme 1).

Decarboxylation of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid: It has been reported¹⁰ that diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid undergoes decarboxylation above its m.p. The compound was heated with HCl, extracted with chloroform, then the chloroform layer on evaporation after proper washing and drying gave a solid which was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to yield the white product, m.p. 55°, C₁₁H₁₁N. M.m.p. with diphenylamine and spectral data confirmed it as diphenylamine.

Bioassay: Toxicity tests of all compounds were carried out in acetone solution. A definite concentration of the solution in solvent (1 ml) was added in thin stream with stirring to mosquito larvae (*Culex* spp.) in water and the toxicity was determined⁹. It was found that at 100 ppm level, diphenylamine and anthranilic acid showed no toxicity to mosquito larvae, but diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid showed 48% toxicity.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded at 90 MHz using TMS as internal reference.

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid: A mixture of anthranilic acid (5 g) and sodium nitrite (5 g) was refluxed in chloroform for 5 h. It was then filtered and the chloroform solution extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The yellow coloured sodium bicarbonate solution was cooled and acidified with HCl carefully at pH 5.5–6, and the resulting brown precipitate was crystallised from benzene–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to yield yellow crystals (1.5%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 73.28; H, 4.80; N, 6.30. C₁₁H₁₁NO₂ Calcd. for: C, 73.23; H, 5.21; N, 6.58%); tlc over silica gel showed homogeneity; λ_{\max} 220 (log ϵ 4.29), 223(4.39), 286(4.17) and 354 nm (3.83); ν_{\max} 3 360 (NH), 1 645 (COOH) and 1 570 cm⁻¹ (Ar); δ 6.80 (ArH), 7.0–7.45, (8×ArH), 8.1 (NH) and 9.4 (COOH).

Decarboxylation of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid: Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (0.3 g) was refluxed with HCl (25 ml) for 2 h. It was then extracted with chloroform and the chloroform layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove unconverted acid. The resulting solid after the removal of chloroform, was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to yield diphenylamine, m.p. 56° (m.m.p. with authentic sample and ir spectra confirmed its identity).

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance. Thanks are also due to the Principal, Durgapur Women's College and authorities of Visva-Bharati for facilities.

References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fortsch. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1977, 34, 279; D. P. CHAKRABORTY, K. O. DAS, B. P. DAS and B. K. CHAUDHURY, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1975, 38, 1.
2. K. SAKANO and S. NAKAMURA, *J. Antibiot.*, 1980, 33, 683; L. M. RICH and K. R. SCOT, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 308; A. A. ASSCHU, L. HUMBER and J. KOMLOSSY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1975, 19, 791; J. G. PERCA and S. M. ALBONICO, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 327; A. MOORADION, P. DUPONT, A. G. HALAAR, M. D. ACETO and J. PAL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 487; D. N. CHOWDHURY and B. P. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, 48, 344; A. SHORB, F. ANWAR, R. S. KAPIL, S. R. POPLI, P. R. DUA and B. N. DHAWAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, 16, 425.
3. B. CHOUHDURY and B. P. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1983, 52, 1130.
4. K. A. GREILMAN, G. M. SHERMAN and H. LINSCHITZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 1881.
5. W. CARRUTHERS, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 272.
6. A. ISLAM, P. BHATTACHARYA and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 537.
7. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1984, 47, 49.
8. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Planta Medica*, 1980, 39, 97.
9. K. H. BÜCHEL, "Chemistry of Pesticides", Wiley, New York, 1983, p. 157.
10. I. HEILBORN, A. H. COOK, H. M. BURBURY and D. H. HEY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 4th. ed., Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1965, Vol. 3, p. 1272.

Synthesis of 4-Benzoyl-3,5-diarylisoxazoles

J. T. GANVIR and V. N. INGLE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 26 May 1987, revised 4 August 1988,
accepted 1 September 1988

3-Benzoyl-2-aryl chromones (1a–e) have been synthesised by the oxidative cyclisation of the corresponding 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones¹. 1a–e on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride yielded the isoxazoles 2a–e. Chincholkar and Jamode² reported the synthesis of some isoxazoles (2) by the interaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and 3-aroil-2-aryl chromones (1). In the present communication we

have extended the reaction to other chromones (1a–e) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride leading to the isoxazoles (2a–e).

3-Benzoyl-2-(4-chlorophenyl) chromone (1a) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid for 1 h, and the resulting clear solution on dilution with water gave a white granular solid (2a) which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145°; it was soluble in dilute NaOH and gave intense violet colour with FeCl₃; ν_{\max} 1 670 (CO), 3 206 (OH), 1 530 (C=N) and 760 cm⁻¹ (isoxazole); δ (CDCl₃) 10.2 (1H, s, OH), 6.84–7.58 (14H, m, ArH). On the basis of these data it was assigned the structure of isoxazole (2a).

On extending the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride to other chromones (1b–e) the corresponding isoxazoles (2b–e) were synthesised (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-BENZOYL-3-ARYL-5-(2-HYDROXYPHENYL)ISOXAZOLES (2)*

Compd. no.	R ¹	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	4-Cl-Phenyl	145	50
2b	3-NO ₂ -Phenyl	161	46
2c	2-Pyridyl	197	71
2d	3-Pyridyl	111	70
2e	4-Pyridyl	197	50

* Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained.

Experimental

Preparation of 4-benzoyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl) isoxazole (2a): A mixture of 3-benzoyl-2-(4-chlorophenyl) chromone (1.7 g), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 g) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The resulting solid after cooling and on addition of excess of water, was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 70; H, 3.2; N, 3.3. C₂₂H₁₄NO₃Cl calcd for: C, 70.4; H, 3.7; N, 3.7%). Purity of 2a was checked by tlc.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. V. Kaulgud, Head, Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University for facilities.